

**IMPLICATION ON EFFECTS OF TECHNOLOGICAL, PEDAGOGICAL AND
CONTENT KNOWLEDGE (TPACK) FRAMEWORK APPLICATION
OF MASTER TEACHERS ON STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE:
BASIS FOR CAPACITY BUILDING**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 20

Issue 10

Pages: 1235-1252

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1927

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11842091

Manuscript Accepted: 05-01-2024

Implication on Effects of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework Application of Master Teachers on Students' Performance: Basis for Capacity Building

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Abstract

This aims to identify the implication of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework on Students' Performance. Purposive sampling was used to identify the respondent schools, stratified random sampling was used to identify the teacher respondents and proportional sampling was used to identify the student respondents. Technological Knowledge, Based on the combined mean of teachers' and students' perception, Master teachers are "Excellent" in "Preparing the instructional materials for different types of learners." With respect to Pedagogical Knowledge, On the combined weighted mean of Master teachers and students, teachers are "Excellent" in "Acting as facilitator and encourages students' leadership roles in activities.". The only "Very Satisfactory" is "Establishing competencies between the lessons and the students' actual environment." With respect to Content Knowledge, Based on the combined computed weighted mean of the perception of the two respondents, Master teachers are "Excellent" in nine items with one "Very Satisfactory". Among the "Excellent" is "Updating the knowledge on the subject matter". The only "Very Satisfactory" is "Utilizing content-based approaches for individual learner". The Level of Students' Academic Performance in terms of Average Grade for the First Quarter is "Very Satisfactory". The following conclusions were drawn from the study: Both Teacher- respondents and student respondents rated teachers as "Very Satisfactory" in the application of the TPACK framework with respect to Technological Knowledge and "Excellent" with respect to Pedagogical Knowledge and Content Knowledge. Both teachers and students are satisfied with pedagogical approaches and mastery of subjects but needs improvement in technological aspects. The academic performance of students who are exposed to TPACK Framework are very satisfactory. The students' performance is related to the framework that the teachers use to deliver their lessons since understanding and performance of students depend on materials, strategies and knowledge of the teachers who discuss the lessons and give their activities. The background of teachers on TPACK framework is related to their teaching competencies as they apply this in their teaching. The perceptions of the respondents vary; however the pedagogical knowledge is viewed with significant difference which may refer to the principles in lesson delivery that also vary from one teacher to another. Content knowledge and technological knowledge are viewed the same since the expected competencies are structured and the technical knowledge of the teacher are of the same level. Teachers' age, sex, strand and highest educational attainment do not affect their utilization of the framework. However, length of service matter since their experience in teaching becomes advantageous. Students' age and grade level do not affect their academic performance. However, students' performance may vary depending upon on their sex since motivation, opinion and focus vary according to sex. The most encountered problem of the Senior High School teachers in applying Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework is the need to identify which specific technologies are best suited for addressing specific learning needs of the students. The best practice of the Senior High School Teachers in Applying Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework is creating an engaging learning environment.

Keywords: *documentary analysis, learning process, TPACK framework, teaching process*

Introduction

Today more than ever, a number of interconnected factors have to be considered for the necessity of teachers' technological advancement, pedagogical competencies and content knowledge for the benefit of the students specifically in achieving commendable academic performance especially master teachers who serve as model for teachers 1-3 since it was observable that with the changing environment and fast-paced development in education some teachers are still left behind. In like manner, to safeguard that teachers are able to go along and comply with the trends and modern way of teaching and learning, the TPACK framework must be utilized and assessed. Master teachers are expected to have more experience in curriculum development, professional development, and mentoring than traditional teacher; they serve as a role model for all other instructional staff and are considered the "gold standard" in teaching (Moore, 2018). They are considered the "crème de la crème" of the teaching profession and their teaching practices will be different from the general, non-master teachers. (Ibrahim, Aziz & Nambiar, 2017).

Since this is the real scenario of the present educational system, the demands for the modern approaches of master teachers in all aspect of teaching is a great need. Likewise, to ensure one hundred percent passing and understanding among students are practically impossible so to achieve success actions must be taken into considerations. Locsin (2019) stated in her study that most often, teachers are blamed for the low performance of the learners. Teacher factor, they say. Poor teachers, who exert effort and sacrifice a lot just to impart knowledge, skills and values to their beloved pupils, still the blame is on them. The teachers have great influence on the

achievement level of pupils but it is not the whole things.

In connection to this, Fauth et al. (2019) revealed that teacher competence (pedagogical content knowledge, self-efficacy, and teaching enthusiasm) was positively related to students' interest; self-efficacy was positively related to student achievement. Three dimensions of teaching quality (cognitive activation, supportive climate, and classroom management), which refer to the actual teacher-student interactions in the classroom, mediated these relationships.

In like manner, to safeguard that teachers are able to go along and comply with the trends and modern way of teaching and learning, the TPACK framework must be utilized. The TPACK framework was introduced by Koehler and Mishra, who originally used the term "technological pedagogical content knowledge," or "TPCK." It aims to integrate technology into the same framework as pedagogy and content. The overarching construct, called technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge (TPACK), has been proposed as the interconnection and intersection of technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge. Locsin (2019) revealed in her study that the background of teachers on TPACK framework is related to their teaching competencies as they apply this in their teaching. The technological background is not significantly related to the teaching competencies as reflected in the Individual Performance Commitment Review Form since the item considering the technology in observation tool is limited. Pedagogical knowledge of teachers varies from one teacher to another since teachers have different principles in lesson delivery. Content knowledge and technological knowledge are viewed the same since the expected competencies are structured and the technical knowledge of the teachers are of the same level.

However, individual teachers in their own subjects used different strategies to address specific problems or issues regarding students' performance. Researchers stress the need for evidence-based, effective, and innovative teaching and learning approaches that can result in not only improved learning outcomes but also greater student wellbeing. Overall, an increasing focus on memorization and testing has been observed in education, including early years, that leaves no space for active exploration and playful learning (Mitchell, 2018), and threatens the wellbeing and socioemotional growth of learners. There is an increased evidence-base that shows that although teachers would like to implement more active, innovative forms of education to meet the diverse learning needs of their students, due to a myriad of constraints teachers often resort to more traditional, conservative approaches to teaching and learning (Herodotou et al., 2019).

It is said that teachers can find a wealth of opportunities to extend their influence and help students and give them extra time. Whitelock, et.al (2019) said that learning is a science and that the testing of learning interventions and teaching approaches before applying these to practice should be a requirement for improving learning outcomes and meeting the expectations of an ever-changing society.

To ensure that school, specifically teachers are doing their best to offer quality education and ensure very good performance among students, DepEd thought of a way that will best guide each institution and this is in accordance with DepEd Order No. 7,s.2010 otherwise known as the Guidelines in the Implementation of the DepEd Computerization" which geared towards the transformation of education system. This improves quality teaching-learning process integrating ICT in the lesson. According to American University's School of Education Online (2020) by integrating technology into existing curricula, as opposed to using it solely as a crisis-management tool, teachers can harness online learning as a powerful educational tool. The effective use of digital learning tools in classrooms can increase student engagement, help teachers improve their lesson plans, and facilitate personalized learning. It also helps students build essential 21st-century skills. Virtual classrooms, video, augmented reality (AR), robots, and other technology tools can not only make class more lively, they can also create more inclusive learning environments that foster collaboration and inquisitiveness and enable teachers to collect data on student performance.

In addition to this, a DepEd Order no. 42, S. 2016 also known as Policy guidelines on Daily Lesson Preparation for the K-12 Basic Education Program was implemented. This provides teachers with an opportunity for reflection on what learners need to learn, how learners learn, and how best to facilitate the learning process. This empower teachers to carry out quality instruction that recognizes the diversity of learners inside the classroom, committed to learners' success, allows the use of varied instructional and formative assessment strategies including the use of ICT and enables the teacher to guide, mentor and support learners in developing and assessing students' learning across the curriculum. The easiest and most practical way that teachers can do to promote their professional development is by doing reflection (Agustin, 2019). Reflection can be done at any time, particularly after the teaching and learning process. More specifically, the reflective practice is integrated into micro-teaching and teaching practicum at higher education programs to promote pre-service teachers for continuous professional development (Widodo, 2018).

These specific DepEd orders aim to strengthen and ensure that all students get the necessary education they deserve. Educators are mandated to take appropriate steps that will safeguard all the needed knowledge of the youth and commendable academic performance. These ensure that teachers integrate technology into the same framework as pedagogy and content for the benefits of students. Diasti and Kuswando (2020) said that technology provides a powerful space that encourages collaboration among practitioners. Online platforms of technology, such as Google Applications, Desire2Learn, Wiki spaces, or Word Press are commonly used as essential tools to support the utilization of reflective practice.

The researcher has observed that there are some teachers who are still having hard time using different applications, programs and even the basic Microsoft office despite of attending seminars or trainings in terms of technology. In terms of pedagogy, teachers are updated

but still others prefer traditional or combination of both. In terms of content knowledge, some teachers are still in confusion or sometimes they are still studying and trying their best to adapt since there some who are not teaching their major subject due to limited teachers or unavailable teachers for specific subject.

With all these and the experiences and exposures of the researcher with different types of students and teachers it pushes him to assess the application of Technological Knowledge, Pedagogical Knowledge and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework on students' academic performance likewise, urges him to conduct this study.

Research Questions

This study sought to assess the application of TPACK:

1. Profile of the Respondents According to:
Master Teachers
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. grade level;
 - 1.4. highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.5. length of service?
2. Students
 - 2.1. age;
 - 2.2. sex; and
 - 2.3. grade level?
 - 2.4. the level of competencies of teachers with respect to:
 - 2.5. Technological Knowledge (TK)
 - 2.6. Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)
 - 2.7. Content Knowledge (CK)?
3. The level of students' academic performance in terms of average grade for the first quarter

Methodology

This section presents the research design, locale, sample and sampling technique, research instrument, data gathering procedure, statistical treatment of data, and ethical consideration.

The researcher used the documentary analysis and descriptive survey. Documentary analysis was used in the study to determine the relationship of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework on Students Academic Performance. The study considered the average grade of the students for the first quarter of the School Year 2022-2023 to identify the academic performance of the students, with this documentary analysis was applied. Permission from DepEd Quezon and from parents will be sought to comply with Data Privacy Act. To identify the Level of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge of teachers, the researcher will gather the result of the distributed the survey questionnaire and the Focus Group Discussion with the students. According to Acosta s cited by Locsin (2019) documentary analysis covers a wide variety of sources, including official statistics, photographs, texts and visual data. She also cited the argumentation of Bloyce that when engage in socio- historical analysis documentary analysis can be useful as a research tool. Documents such as newspaper, books, magazines and government minutes can be read and preserved so that they are available for analysis by the social researcher as she cited too from Bryman. The extent of their relevance depends on the validity, reliability and adequacy of the documents gathered.

Another method used is the descriptive survey. Descriptive research refers to the method used in exploring a query or subject wherein it measures results instead of trying to predict outcomes or actions to determine results.

According to Ibay as cited by Locsin (2019), descriptive research is used to describe characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. It addresses the "what" questions. The characteristics used to describe the situation or populations are usually some kind of categorical scheme also known as descriptive categories. Descriptive research generally precedes explanatory research. The goal is the acquisition of factual, accurate and systematic data that can be used in average, frequencies and similar statistical calculations. Descriptive studies seldom involve experimentation as they are more concerned with naturally occurring phenomenon than with the observation of controlled situations.

This descriptive survey was used to assess the application of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework on students' academic performance.

The study was conducted at the public Junior High Schools in the First Congressional District in the Division of Quezon.

Quezon's 1st congressional district is one of the four congressional districts of the Philippines in the province of Quezon, formerly Tayabas. It has been represented in the House of Representatives of the Philippines since 1916 and earlier in the Philippine Assembly from 1907 to 1916. The district consists of Quezon's former capital city of Tayabas and adjacent municipalities of Burdeos, General

Nakar, Infanta, Jomalig, Lucban, Mauban, Pagbilao, Panukulan, Patnanungan, Polillo, Real and Sampaloc.

Technological and instructional skills and mastery of the subject are vital factors in pursuing quality education. Since the aim of the Division of Quezon is to offer quality education, this study will be beneficial to the division.

The subject of the study included the implication of technological, pedagogical and content knowledge of teachers on students' academic performance. This mainly focuses on assessing the level of application of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework on Students' Academic Performance specifically the Araling Panlipunan Master Teachers of JHS.

A questionnaire check list, the average grade of the students for the first quarter and the Focus Group Discussion will be the main instruments in gathering the needed data. The questionnaire-checklist and the Focus Group Discussion contain series of questions identifying the knowledge and practices of teachers relating to their technological, pedagogical and content knowledge. The gathering of data was administered by the researcher to further explain the content of the questionnaire and interviews. The data was gathered during the School Year 2022-2023.

The total sample population of the respondents was simply a representation from nine (9) selected public JHS schools in the province of Quezon.

Upon the approval of the title of the study and proposal defense, the researcher gathered the data of the respondents in the first congressional district in the Division of Quezon. The researcher purposely choose the subject schools and utilized stratified random sampling to determine the teacher respondents and proportional sampling for student respondents.

The permit to conduct the study was sought from the Schools Division Superintendent and the Dean of the Graduate Studies.

The researcher adopted and modify a questionnaire checklist; sought the help of the experts to validate the questionnaire checklist then conduct the survey, test the reliability, the FGD and the average grade of the students for the first quarter for the School Year 2022-2023 to gather the needed data. The results of these serve as guides for the researcher to identify the implication of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework on Students' Academic Performance.

After this, answers were thoroughly interpreted and analyzed to draw conclusions and recommendations to be offered. After this, the manuscript will be submitted to the adviser for critiquing for the preparation of presentation of the result.

Since the data assessed the Applications of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework on Students' Academic Performance, two instruments were used in gathering the data needed.

The researcher adopted and enhance a survey questionnaire that identified the technological, pedagogical and content knowledge of teachers. To find out the academic performance of the students, the average grades for the first quarter were utilized using documentary analysis. These primary sources were the main source of the needed data.

To check the validity of the items to be included in the research instrument, the researcher seeks the help of the experts who gave suggestions and comments on the instruments. After it passed through content validation by the persons knowledgeable in the field of research and tested its reliability statistics, it will distributed in the different schools in the first Congressional District in the division of Quezon.

Given below is the scale range with the corresponding verbal interpretation of the responses.

Responses from the Questionnaire Checklist

<i>Scale</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
4.20 - 5.00	Excellent
3.40 -4.19	If you always do it, 85%-100% practiced/witnessed
2.60 -3.39	Very Satisfactory
1.80- 2.59	If you do it frequently, 70%-84% practiced/witnessed
1.00-1.79	Satisfactory
	If you do it occasionally, 55%-69% practiced/witnessed
	Fairly Satisfactory
	If you do it rarely, 40% - 54% practiced/witnessed
	Poor
	If you do it for only 39 % and below. Very limited is witnessed or never witnessed

In selecting the teacher respondents, stratified random sampling technique will be used using Slovin's Formula with 5% margin of error.

Stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller groups known as strata. In stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics.

Stratified random sampling is also called proportional purposive sampling or quota random sampling. To select the student respondents

the researcher used proportional sampling. Proportional sampling is a sampling strategy used when the population is composed of several subgroups that are vastly different in number.

To answer the problem presented the following statistical tools were used: 1) To determine profile of the respondents, frequency, percentage and rank distribution will be used. 2) To determine the level of competencies of teachers, weighted mean was used. 3) To determine the level of students' academic performance, documentary analysis was used. 4.) To determine the level of performance of Senior High School teachers as revealed by their Individual Performance Commitment Review Form (IPCRF), documentary analysis was used. 5.) To determine the significant relationship between the level of competencies of teachers with respect to TPACK framework and students' academic performance, Pearson R Correlation was used. 6.) To determine the relationship between the level of competencies of teachers with respect to TPACK Framework and the IPCRF results, Pearson R Correlation was used. 7.) To determine the difference between the level of competencies of teachers with respect to TPACK framework as assessed by the two groups of respondents, T- test was used. 8.) To determine the difference between the level of competencies of teachers with respect to TPACK framework in terms of teachers' profile, F- test one way annova was used. 9.) To determine the difference on the level of academic performance of the students in terms of their profile, F-test one way ANOVA was used.

Results and Discussion

This section briefly presents the results, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered based on the problems presented in the research.

Profile of Master teachers

Table 2 on the next page presents the profile of Master.

Table 2. *Profile of Master teachers*

<i>Age</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Below 30	11	22.0	3
31 – 40	19	38.0	1
41 – 50	17	34.0	2
51 Above	3	6.0	4
Total	50	100.0	
<i>Sex</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Male	13	26.0	2
Female	37	74.0	1
Total	50	100.0	
<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Rank</i>
7	12	24.0	3
8	12	24.0	3
9	12	24.0	3
10	14	28.0	1
Total	50	100.0	
<i>Educational Attainment</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Bachelor's Degree	6	12.0	3
with units in MS/MA/MAEd	20	40.0	2
MS/MA/MAEd graduate	21	42	1
with units in Ed.D/Ph.D.	2	4.0	4
Ed.D/Ph.D. graduate	1	2.0	5
Total	50	100.0	
<i>Length of Service</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Rank</i>
0-2	1	2.0	5
3-5	9	18.0	4
6 - 8	11	22.0	3
9 - 11	15	30.0	1
12 Above	14	28.0	2
Total	50	100.0	

It can be gleaned from the table that most of the teacher respondents came from Grade 10 with a percentage of 28 while the others were equally distributed from Grade 7, 8 and 9 with a percentage of 24. 38% of the teacher respondents are already 31 - 40 years old. Most of them are female with a percentage of 74.0. They are serving the public school for 9-11 years with a percentage of 30. 0. Most of the teachers acquired their units in Masters Degree with a percentage of 42.

The results implied that most of the teachers are in the right age and have enough experience since they are already in the service for 9 to 11 years implying that they acquired the required competencies to teach the subject they handle most especially that they acquired their Masters Degree.

This was proven by the study of Locsin (2019) as she cited the work of Agellon. She mentioned that personal characteristics of a person

is positively associated with his/her performance. Older individuals can easily adapt to his environment and solve problems without difficulty.

Profile of students

Table 3. *Profile of the students*

Age	Student		Rank
	F	%	
12	94	17.9	4
13	126	24.0	3
14	148	28.1	1
15	130	24.7	2
16	28	5.3	5
Total	526	100	
Sex			
Male	215	40.9	2
Female	311	59.1	1
Total	526	100.0	
Grade 11			
7	132	25.1	2
8	132	25.1	2
9	132	25.1	2
10	130	24.7	4
Total	455	100.0	

It can be gleaned from the table that most of the student respondents were equally distributed among grades 7,8 and 9 with a percentage of 25.1 while grade 10 had 24.7 percentage. 28.1 % of the student respondents are 14 years old. Most of them are female with a percentage of 59.1.

The results implied that most of the students are in the right age and have direct contact and know their teachers that much since they are their subject teachers and some are their advisers.

This was proven by the study of Locsin (2019) as she cited the work of Agellon. She mentioned that personal characteristics of a person is positively associated with his/her performance. Older individuals can easily adapt to his environment and solve problems without difficulty.

Level of Competencies of Master Teachers in the Application of TPACK Framework with respect to Technological Knowledge

Table 4. *Perception of the Master teachers and Students on the level of competencies of Master teachers in the application of TPACK framework with respect to Technological Knowledge*

Technological Knowledge	Teacher			Student			Overall		
	Mean	VI	Rank	Mean	VI	Rank	Mean	VI	Rank
1. Using improvised and indigenized materials for instruction.	4.08	VS	8	3.84	VS	10	3.88	VS	10
2. Applying the principles in instructional material preparations.	4.27	E	1.5	4.22	E	2	4.23	E	2
3. Preparing the instructional materials for different types of learners.	4.12	VS	6	4.29	E	1	4.26	E	1
4. Designing ICT- based Instructional materials with digital resources.	4.27	E	1.5	4.17	VS	4	4.19	VS	3
5. Exposing students to E- instructional resources such as E-books, hyperlinks, and computer-assisted activities.	3.91	VS	10	4.00	VS	7	3.99	VS	8
6. Operating ICT systems as applied in the teaching and learning process.	4.14	VS	4.5	4.13	VS	5	4.13	VS	5
7. Educating students in the social responsibility, ethical and legal use of ICT tools and resources.	4.15	VS	3	4.18	VS	3	4.18	VS	4
8. Preparing advanced evaluation tools using technology.	3.92	VS	9	4.10	VS	6	4.07	VS	6
9. Involving students to various activities involving technology.	4.14	VS	4.5	3.97	VS	8	4.00	VS	7
10. Letting students explore the lessons using digital resources.	4.11	VS	7	3.85	VS	9	3.89	VS	9
Grand Mean	4.11	VS		4.07	VS		4.08	VS	

Legend: VS- Very Satisfactory; E- Excellent

It can be seen from the table that the Master teachers perceived that they are “Excellent” in item no. 2 “Applying the principles in instructional material preparations” and item no. 4 Designing ICT-based instructional materials with digital resources” which both

garnered an average mean of 4.27 and ranked as number 1. However, teachers considered item no. 5 “Exposing students to E-instructional resources such as E-Books, hyperlinks, and computer-assisted activities.” as their weakness which has an average mean of 3.91 and ranked as number 10.

For students, they perceived that their teachers are “Excellent” in item no. 3 which is “Preparing the instructional materials for different types of learners.” with the average mean of 4.29 and ranked as no. 1 and item no. 2 “Applying the principles in instructional material preparations.” With an average mean of 4.22 and ranked as no. 2 while the least for them is “Using improvised and indigenized materials for instruction with an average mean of 3.84.

Based on the combined mean of Master teachers’ and students’ perception, teachers are “Excellent” in item no. 3 which is “Preparing the instructional materials for different types of learners.” with the average mean of 4.26 and ranked as no. 1 while the least for them is “Using improvised and indigenized materials for instruction with an average mean of 3.88.

The result implies that with respect to Technological Knowledge, for teachers they are excellent in applying the principles in instructional material preparations and in designing ICT-based instructional materials with digital resources. However, they are weak in exposing students to E- instructional resources such as E-Books, hyperlinks, and computer-assisted activities. While for students, their teachers are excellent in preparing the instructional materials for different types of learners and applying the principles in instructional material preparations but weak in using improvised and indigenized materials for instruction. This may mean that master teachers are competent in preparing instructional materials using the technology that are suitable to different types of learners. They are able to follow the principles in the preparations that is they can improvise or use ICT-based instructional materials. However, students don’t consider the design excellent.

This can be supported by the study of McKnight et. al. (2017). They found out that when technology is used to remodel learning routines, cognitive processes, problem solving, and teacher roles, the schools can realize the promise of technology to transform learning. Technology has the potential to be dynamic instructional tool to promote student learning. This proves that through technology master teachers will be able improve their instructional materials and strategies.

Level of Competencies of Master Teachers in the Application of TPACK Framework with respect to Pedagogical Knowledge

Table 5. Level of Competencies of Master Teachers in the Application of TPACK Framework with respect to Pedagogical Knowledge

	Pedagogical Knowledge	Teacher			Student			Overall		
		Mean	VI	Rank	Mean	VI	Rank	Mean	VI	Rank
1.	Providing interactive activities to encourage maximum participation among the students.	4.39	E	4	4.30	E	1.5	4.32	E	2
2.	Acting as facilitator and encourages students’ leadership roles in activities.	4.46	E	2	4.30	E	1.5	4.33	E	1
3.	Providing questions based on the level of the students.	4.49	E	1	4.26	E	4	4.30	E	3
4.	Varying the questioning technique to elicit critical thinking among the students.	4.41	E	3	4.24	E	7	4.27	E	5
5.	Engaging students to varied activities to deliver the lessons.	4.35	E	6.5	4.25	E	6	4.27	E	5
6.	Adopting or innovating techniques in teaching the lessons.	4.35	E	6.5	4.26	E	4	4.27	E	5
7.	Monitoring the performances of the students in every activity through monitoring evaluation tools.	4.28	E	9	4.20	E	8	4.22	E	8
8.	Providing feedback mechanism to students to evaluate their performance and serves as basis for improvement.	4.32	E	8	4.17	VS	10	4.20	E	9
9.	Establishing competencies between the lessons and the students’ actual environment.	4.24	E	10	4.18	VS	9	4.19	VS	10
10.	Delivering lesson in contextual situation.	4.38	E	5	4.26	E	4	4.28	E	4
	Grand Mean	4.37	E		4.24	E		4.26	E	

Legend: VS- Very Satisfactory; E- Excellent

Perusal to the table is the perception of Master teachers on the application of TPACK framework with respect to Pedagogical Knowledge which revealed that Master teachers are all “Excellent” in the given items but among all these rank 1 is the item no. 3 “Providing questions based on the level of the students.” with a weighted mean of 4.49 while the last in rank is item no. 9 “Establishing competencies between the lessons and the students’ actual environment.”

For the student-respondents, their teachers are “Very Satisfactory” in only two items which are nos. 8 and 9 “Providing feedback mechanism to students to evaluate their performance and serves as basis for improvement.” and item no. 9 “Establishing competencies between the lessons and the students’ actual environment.” with a weighted mean of 4.20 and 4.19 respectively while the remaining items are all “Excellent”. Top among these are item no. 1 “Providing interactive activities to encourage maximum participation among the students.” and item no. 2 “Acting as facilitator and encourages students’ leadership roles in activities.” with

both 4.30 weighted mean.

As reflected on the combined weighted mean of Master teachers and students, teachers are “Excellent” in 9 items no. 2 being the rank 1 which is “Acting as facilitator and encourages students’ leadership roles in activities.” with 4.33 weighted. The only “Very Satisfactory” is item no. 9 “Establishing competencies between the lessons and the students’ actual environment.” with a weighted mean of 4.19.

It can be deduced from the results that, with respect to Pedagogical Knowledge, teachers believe that they are excellent in Providing questions based on the level of the students but need to improve in establishing competencies between the lessons and the students’ actual environment while for the student, their teachers are very satisfactory in providing feedback mechanism to students to evaluate their performance and serves as basis for improvement and in establishing competencies between the lessons and the students’ actual environment. This means that teachers are very competent in almost all aspects of pedagogical approach specially in using (Higher Order Thinking) HOT questions with minimal improvement in relating learning to real life situation but there is a need to address the concerns of the students specifically how they provide feedback mechanism to students to evaluate their performance and serves as basis for improvement. With the contradicting assessment of teachers and students, specifically in providing feedback mechanism to students to evaluate their performance and serves as basis for improvement and establishing competencies between the lessons and the students’ actual environment, there is a need to address this needs for improvement. With that it will serve as a basis for the output of the study which is capacity building.

The result is supported by the study of Herrington, Bancroft, Edwards and Schairer (2017) which states that teachers’ self-assessment in the different TPACK domains may be used as a method of measuring their beliefs related in these domains. This can be used as a guide for improvement. This study supported the claims of the researchers that it is important to assess the performance of the teachers and it should be in many aspects and ways. Self-assessment may be supported by students assessment since they are the direct customers of the teachers.

Level of Competencies of Master Teachers in the Application of TPACK Framework with respect to Content Knowledge

Table 6. *Level of Competencies of Master Teachers in the Application of TPACK Framework with respect to Content Knowledge as perceived by the teachers and students*

	Content Knowledge	Teacher			Student			Overall		
		Mean	VI	Rank	Mean	VI	Rank	Mean	VI	Rank
1.	Updating the knowledge on the subject matter.	4.52	E	2	4.49	E	1	4.49	E	1
2.	Designing lessons with congruent objectives, teaching methods, learning activities and materials.	4.53	E	1	4.39	E	4	4.41	E	3
3.	Utilizing Content-based approaches for individual learners	4.32	E	7.5	4.17	VS	10	4.19	VS	10
4.	Organizing the topics or contents to be easily understood.	4.37	E	4	4.46	E	2	4.45	E	2
5.	Encouraging critical thinking among students.	4.45	E	3	4.27	E	7.5	4.30	E	7
6.	Applying teacher-made test appropriate to the expected competencies of the students.	4.35	E	6	4.37	E	5	4.37	E	5
7.	Integrating scholarly and relevant works/ideas to deepen the content background.	4.25	E	9	4.21	E	9	4.21	E	9
8.	Exposing students to scholarly researches to discover the concepts independently.	4.09	VS	10	4.27	E	7.5	4.24	E	8
9.	Focusing on learning competencies to formulate the instructional objectives.	4.36	E	5	4.32	E	6	4.33	E	6
10.	Providing authentic activities that engage students to apply the concepts learned in life-like scenario.	4.32	E	7.5	4.40	E	3	4.38	E	4
Grand Mean		4.35	E		4.33	E		4.34	E	

Legend: VS- Very Satisfactory; E- Excellent

The table revealed that Master teachers perceived that their Level of Competencies in the Application of TPACK Framework with respect to Content Knowledge is “Excellent” in nine items. Among these, item no. 2 “Designing lessons with congruent objectives, teaching methods, learning activities and materials” is considered as rank 1 with a computed weighted mean of 4.53. The only “Very Satisfactory” item is no. 8 “Exposing students to scholarly researches to discover the concepts independently” with a computed weighted mean of 4.09.

Meanwhile, the students perceived almost the same with their teachers. They considered their teachers “Excellent” in nine items too. Among these, item no. 1 “Updating the knowledge on the subject matter is considered as rank 1 with a computed weighted mean of 4.49. The only “Very Satisfactory for them is item no. 3 “Utilizing content-based approaches for individual learner” with a computed weighted mean of 4.17.

Based on the combined computed weighted mean of the perception of the two respondents, Master teachers are “Excellent” in nine items with one “Very Satisfactory”. Among the “Excellent” item no. 1 “Updating the knowledge on the subject matter” is rank 1 with a computed weighted mean of 4.9. The only “Very Satisfactory” is item no. 3 “Utilizing content-based approaches for individual learner” with a computed weighted mean of 4.17.

This implies that intents should be given more emphasis as to how individual learners may master the lesson well. Teachers perceived that they are excellent in designing lessons with congruent objectives, teaching methods, learning activities and materials but can improve more in exposing students to scholarly researches to discover the concepts independently. Meanwhile, the students perceived that their teachers are excellent in updating the knowledge on the subject matter but need to improve in utilizing content-based approaches for individual learner.

It can be further implied from the result that teachers and students believe that Master teachers are very competent in applying the TPACK framework with respect to Content Knowledge. They are excellent in almost all aspects specifically in designing, planning and delivering the lessons with minimal improvement on teaching approaches for individual learners. This may mean that teachers need to further improve or make necessary adjustment in addressing the individual needs of the students especially in exposing students to scholarly researches to discover the concepts independently and in utilizing content-based approaches for individual learner.

This is aligned to what Locsin (2019) had cited in her study which stated that skills that contributed to the effectiveness of teachers are knowledge of teaching models and curriculum, understanding learners and content knowledge. This is proves that technology and strategies could not go alone they should be supported by teachers’ knowledge of the lessons.

Level of Academic Performance of Students in terms of Average Grade for the First Quarter

Table 7. *Level of Academic Performance of Students in terms of Average Grade for the First Quarter*

	Mean	Sd.	VI
General Average of Student	88.05	4.915	VS

Legend: VS- Very Satisfactory

The table shows that the Level of Students’ Academic Performance in terms of Average Grade for the First Quarter is “Very Satisfactory” with a mean of 88.05 and standard deviation of 4.915.

The result implies that students are motivated to perform well in their class since the result of their grade manifests that they perform well. The grades of the students clearly revealed that students have commendable academic performance. This also proves that the performance of teachers reflects on the performance of students. As the result of assessment, teachers are excellent if not at least very satisfactory in TPACK framework which was justified but the result of students’ performance.

Furthermore, this can be proven too as the pandemic occurred and all teachers are shifting to other mode of learnings and all were trying to adapt, this too reflects to low performance of students.

This result is supported by the study of Oredina and Ebueza (2020). They stated that competent teachers are the most influential factor in bringing high students’ achievement. The teachers greatly influence the students’ performance through their abilities, potentialities and professional competence. Only competent teachers can bring desired learning among their students. This proves the claim of the researcher that the performance of the teachers reflects on the performance of the students.

Test of Significance between the Level of Competencies of Master Teachers with respect to TPACK Framework in terms of Age

Table 8. *The significant difference between the level of Competencies of Teachers with respect to TPACK Framework in terms of Age*

	SV	SS	df	MS	f	Sig.	Ho	VI
Technological Knowledge (TK)	Between Groups	1.113	3	.371	1.144	.336	FR	NS
	Within Groups	26.586	82	.324				
	Total	27.699	85					
Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)	Between Groups	.911	3	.304	1.702	.173	FR	NS
	Within Groups	14.633	82	.178				
	Total	15.544	85					
Content Knowledge (CK)	Between Groups	1.741	3	.580	2.663	.053	FR	NS
	Within Groups	17.865	82	.218				
	Total	19.606	85					

Legend: Not Significant

As shown in the table, it was statistically found out that there is No Significant difference on the level of competencies of teachers with respect to technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge in terms of age obtaining probability value of .336, .173 and .053 respectively.

The result implies that age of teachers does not matter in the utilization of the TPACK framework. Their adaptation on technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge (TPACK) framework do not merely rely on their age. Teachers, as they aged perform better and developed more skills to comply with needs of the framework. Moreover, what ever the age of the teachers, they are all equally trained by the schools through LAC sessions and mentoring.

This was proven by the study of Locsin (2019) as she cited Agellon as he stated that age of a person is positively associated with his/her performance. Older individuals can easily adapt to his environment and solve problems without difficulty. And since the respondents of the study is already in right age, it shows that it doesn't affect the utilization of the framework.

Test of Significance between the Level of Competencies of Teachers with respect to TPACK Framework in terms of Sex

Table 9. *The significant difference between the level of Competencies of Teachers with respect to TPACK Framework in terms of sex*

	SV	SS	df	MS	f	Sig.	Ho	VI
Technological Knowledge (TK)	Between Groups	.857	1	.857	2.761	.100	FR	NS
	Within Groups	27.630	89	.310				
	Total	28.487	90					
Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)	Between Groups	.000	1	.000	.001	.981	FR	NS
	Within Groups	16.155	89	.182				
	Total	16.155	90					
Content Knowledge (CK)	Between Groups	.003	1	.003	.015	.904	FR	NS
	Within Groups	20.168	89	.227				
	Total	20.171	90					

Legend: Not Significant

As presented in the table, it was statistically found out that there is No Significant difference on the level of competencies of teachers with respect to technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge in terms of sex with probability values of .100, .981 and .904 respectively.

The result connotes that sex of teachers does not matter in applying the TPACK framework in their teaching. Sex does not affect the application of the TPACK framework since both sexes are required to acquire skills in all competencies to be able to comply with the needs of performing teachers. And as observed, whatever the sex of the teachers, they both utilized all aspects of TPACK framework.

This contrast the result of the study of Agellon (2017) since he said that sex influence the performance of an individual because suitability of tasks varied. This negate the result since it was revealed in the study that sex does not really matter in the utilization of the framework.

Test of Significance between the Level of Competencies of Teachers with respect to TPACK Framework in terms of grade level

Table 10. *The significant difference between the level of Competencies of Teachers with respect to TPACK Framework in terms of grade level*

	SV	SS	df	MS	f	Sig.	Ho	VI
Technological Knowledge (TK)	Between Groups	1.309	5	.262	.769	.575	FR	NS
	Within Groups	25.182	74	.340				
	Total	26.491	79					
Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)	Between Groups	.572	5	.114	.581	.715	FR	NS
	Within Groups	14.577	74	.197				
	Total	15.149	79					
Content Knowledge (CK)	Between Groups	1.022	5	.204	.814	.544	FR	NS
	Within Groups	18.584	74	.251				
	Total	19.606	79					

Legend: Not Significant

The table reveals that it was statistically found out that there is No Significant difference on the level of competencies of teachers with respect to technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge in terms of grade level obtaining probability values of .575, .715 and .544 respectively

By implication, grade level cannot be considered as one of the factors that may affect the utilization of the TPACK framework. Whatever the grade level of the teachers, their skills in applying the framework are not affected since teachers use appropriate aspect of the framework depending upon on the level of their students.

This was strengthened by the book of Borg (2017) which stated that teachers' knowledge. is practical because much of what teachers know originates in practices and this practices vary depending on the level of the students that they have.

Test of Significance between the Level of Competencies of Teachers with respect to TPACK Framework in terms of Highest Educational Attainments

Table 11. Reveals the significant difference between the level of Competencies of Teachers with respect to TPACK Framework in terms of highest educational attainment.

Table 11. *The significant difference between the level of Competencies of Teachers with respect to TPACK Framework in terms of highest educational attainment*

	SV	SS	df	MS	f	Sig.	Ho	VI
Technological Knowledge (TK)	Between Groups	2.337	4	.584	1.937	.111	FR	NS
	Within Groups	26.236	87	.302				
	Total	28.573	91					
Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)	Between Groups	1.267	4	.317	1.837	.129	FR	NS
	Within Groups	15.000	87	.172				
	Total	16.267	91					
Content Knowledge (CK)	Between Groups	.809	4	.202	.899	.468	FR	NS
	Within Groups	19.563	87	.225				
	Total	20.372	91					

Legend: Not Significant

As presented in the table, it was statistically found out that there is No Significant difference on the level of competencies of teachers with respect to technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge in terms of highest educational attainment with probability values of .111, .129 and .468 respectively.

This implied that educational background of teachers does not contribute in the application of the TPACK framework. Their skills in applying the TPACK framework are not affected by their educational achievements since the competencies associated with the TPACK framework may also be acquired through various seminars and training which are offered by DepEd or through LAC sessions.

Rosier (2017) stated that schools need highly qualified, expert teachers to improve the quality of education, and an advanced degree tells a school you are valuable, knowledgeable teacher that will have most impact on your students and highly qualified teachers may be trained through various seminars and training which are offered by DepEd or through LAC sessions.

Test of Significance between the Level of Competencies of Teachers with respect to TPACK Framework in terms of length of Service

Table 12. *The significant difference between the level of Competencies of Teachers with respect to TPACK Framework in terms of length of service*

	SV	SS	df	MS	f	Sig.	Ho	VI
Technological Knowledge (TK)	Between Groups	.761	4	.190	.597	.666	FR	NS
	Within Groups	25.173	79	.319				
	Total	25.934	83					
Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)	Between Groups	1.703	4	.426	2.514	.048	R	S
	Within Groups	13.380	79	.169				
	Total	15.083	83					
Content Knowledge (CK)	Between Groups	1.418	4	.355	1.641	.172	FR	NS
	Within Groups	17.073	79	.216				
	Total	18.492	83					

Legend: S- Significant; NS: Not Significant

As shown in the table, it was statistically found out that there is No Significant difference on the level of competencies of teachers with respect to technological knowledge and content knowledge in terms of length of service. These obtained probability values of .666 and .172 respectively. However, it was found out that pedagogical knowledge has Significant difference on the level of competencies of teachers in terms of length service with a probability value of .048.

The result implied that seasoned teachers have advantage in applying the TPACK framework. Teachers who have more experience can easily adjust and apply the framework since they already acquire so much knowledge and experience in applying teaching strategies as they acquired more years in teaching. They have edge in accumulating more knowledge and experience as they have longer years in the profession.

This was proven by Comighud,, Futlan and Cordevilla (2020) who cited the study of Wuah who noted that teachers, being in a service for a long time, are aware of the duties they are expected to perform. Furthermore, they mentioned too that teachers know their personal responsibilities, rights, and functions. They were already responsible to implement the curriculum. This is proven in the result of the study since it was revealed that teachers who are exposed in the profession for years are more advantageous.

Test of Significance on the Level of Academic Performance of the Students in terms of Age, Sex and Grade Level.

Table 13 reveals the significant difference on the Level of Academic Performance of the Students in terms of age, sex and grade level.

As can be seen in the table, it was statistically found out that there is No Significant difference on the level of academic performance of the students in terms of age and grade level with obtained probability values of .605 and .102 respectively. However, it was found out that sex has Significant difference on the level of academic performance with a probability value of .005.

Table 13. *Test of Significance on the Level of Academic Performance of the Students in terms Age, Sex and Grade Level*

		SV	SS	df	MS	f	Sig.	Ho	VI
Age	Between Groups	16.437	39	.421	.923	.605	FR	NS	
	Within Groups	175.298	384	.457					
	Total	191.736	423						
Sex	Between Groups	14.957	39	.384	1.751	.005	R	S	
	Within Groups	84.304	385	.219					
	Total	99.261	424						
Grade Level	Between Groups	98.995	39	2.538	1.318	.102	FR	NS	
	Within Groups	745.454	387	1.926					
	Total	844.450	426						

Legend: S- Significant; NS: Not Significant

The result connotes that performance of students does not vary in their age and grade level but it may differ depending on sex since focus, opinion and motivation vary depending on their sexual identity. Grade level is mandatory which means the students' skills are inclined to it and hone depending on each level. Age is just a number that could not be solely use as a basis of understanding a specific matter. This my mean too that sex of students is really a considerable factor since personality of male and female varies specially on focus and dedication to studies.

This result is proven by Shapiro and Stefkovich (2017). They mentioned in their book that perception and performance vary depending on gender. Furthermore, Whitbourn (2018) said that age may not be a good indicator of the performance and condition of a person. This proves the claim of the researcher that personality of male and female varies specially on focus and dedication to studies which can be resulted to different academic performance.

Test of significance on the level of competencies of teachers with respect to TPACK Framework as assessed by two groups of respondents

Table 14. *The significant difference between the level of competencies of teachers with respect to TPACK framework as assessed by the two groups of respondents*

	Respondent	Mean	Sd.	Mean Diff.	t	df	Sig.	Ho	VI
Technological Knowledge (TK)	Teacher	4.11	.560	.035	.494	545	.621	FR	NS
	Student	4.07	.631						
Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)	Teacher	4.37	.423	.129	2.468	542	.015	R	S
	Student	4.24	.598						
Content Knowledge (CK)	Teacher	4.35	.473	.022	.323	542	.747	FR	NS
	Student	4.33	.602						

Legend: S- Significant; NS: Not Significant

The test on significant difference on the perception of Master Teachers and Students with regards to Utilization of Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework reveals that there is No Significance difference between the perception of teachers and students with respect to Technological Knowledge with mean difference of .035. With respect to Pedagogical Knowledge, it was found out that there is Significant difference between the two with a mean difference of .129. Moreover, the views of the two sets of respondents with respect to Content Knowledge are Not Significantly different with a mean difference of .022.

The result connotes that students proved the personal assessment of teachers that they are really performing excellently in utilizing the TPACK framework especially in Technological and Content Knowledge. However, teachers need time to reflect and evaluate themselves in their pedagogical knowledge since students slightly don't agree with it. Furthermore, teachers need to consider that pedagogical knowledge is contributory to students' academic performance. Tasks given should be evaluated and improved. Teachers must be aware that their performance reflect on students' performance, with this, if teachers improved students will also improve.

Bustos-Orosa (2019) shared that excellent teachers have two types of attribute: technical skill (content, organization, applicability) and personal skills (attitude, empathy). These two were considered as factors affecting academic performance of students. And as the results of the study revealed these two factors are part of the competencies that the teachers have to improve.

Test of Significance in Relationship between the level of competencies of Master Teachers with respect to TPACK Framework and students’ Academic Performance

As shown in the table, it was statistically found out that there is significant relationship between the Technological knowledge of teachers and students’ academic performance. With respect to Pedagogical knowledge and students’ academic performance, it was revealed that they are also significantly related, Moreover, Content knowledge of teachers and students’ Academic Performance is significantly related too. Since the obtained probability values of .021, .002 and .003 respectively exceeds at .05 level.

The result implies that teachers’ performance is significantly related to students’ performance. If the teachers have higher competencies they reflect on students’ academic performance, with this, the students acquire the same competencies and able to perform well. If the teachers have very good performance, the students are very good as well. Moreover, technological knowledge has very limited contribution on students’ performance but pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge of teachers motivate them to strive. This may mean too that whether the teachers use cartolina or manila paper or poster as long as they apply effective strategy and they are knowledgeable with the topic they will be commendable. Teachers must realized that being the best in all aspects of the framework are non-negotiable since they are the key instruments in achieving commendable learning process.

Table 15. *The significant relationship between the level of competencies of Master Teachers with respect to TPACK framework and students’ Academic Performance*

TPACK Framework	Pearson-r	VI	Sig.	Ho	VI
Technological Knowledge (TK)	.111	Very Low Correlation	.021	R	S
Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)	.149	Negligible Correlation	.002	R	S
Content Knowledge (CK)	.145	Negligible Correlation	.003	R	S
Grand Mean	.143	Negligible Correlation	.003	R	S

Legend: S- Significant

As Hakim (2019) said in his study, teachers ‘competencies have simultaneously or jointly declared significant influence in improving the quality of performance in the learning process. This proves that teachers’ competencies are the roots of effective teaching-learning process.

Students’ assessment on the Technological Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) and Content Knowledge (CK) of their teachers in terms of problems encountered

Table 16.1. *The Students’ assessment on the Technological Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) and Content Knowledge (CK) of their teachers in terms of problems encountered*

Problems Encountered	Teacher			Students			Overall		Rank
	f	%	Rank	F	%	Rank	f	%	
1. It is hard to incorporate all necessary elements that will help learners to acquire the necessary competencies.	48	52.2	5	228	50.1	7	276	50.5	7
2. The need to identify which specific technologies are best suited for addressing specific learning needs of the students	55	59.8	3	342	75.2	1	397	72.6	1
3. Entails a deeper understanding of the constraints and affordances of technologies.	37	40.2	6	321	70.5	2	358	65.4	2
4. Instructional design	34	37.0	7	267	58.7	4	301	55.0	5
5. Computer literacy	32	34.8	8	304	66.8	3	336	61.4	3
6. Limited resources	70	76.1	1	257	56.5	5	327	59.8	4
7. Limited trainings/ workshop	64	69.6	2				64	11.7	10
8. Lack of supported values and beliefs, infrastructure and models to guide the development of expertise.	34	37.0	10	200	44.0	8	234	42.8	8
9. Limited time in preparations and class hours.	49	53.3	4	243	53.4	6	292	53.4	6
10. Current School situation is not conducive to developing TPACK.	31	33.7	9	158	34.7	9	189	34.6	9

As shown in the table, the teacher-respondents considered item no. 6 “Limited Resources” as the most encountered problem in applying Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework with a percentage of 76.1 and ranked as number one and the least encountered is item no. 8 “Lack of supported values and beliefs, infrastructure and models to guide the development of expertise.” With a percentage of 37.0 and ranked as number ten.

Meanwhile, student-respondents considered item no. 2 “The need to identify which specific technologies are best suited for addressing specific learning needs of the students.” as the most encountered problem in applying Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework with a percentage of 75.2 and ranked as number one while the least encountered problem is item no.

10 “Current School situation is not conducive to developing TPACK.” With a percentage of 34.7 and ranked as number 9 No one answered item no. 7 “Limited trainings/workshop” because students are not aware of it.

Based on the overall result, students believe that the most encountered problem of the Master teachers in applying Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework is item no. 2 “The need to identify which specific technologies are best suited for addressing specific learning needs of the students.” with a percentage of 72.6 and ranked no. 1. The least encountered problem is item no. 7 “Limited trainings/workshop” with 11.7 % and ranked as number 10.

It can be noted from the result that the teachers considered limited resources as the most encountered problem in applying Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework while for students is the need to identify which specific technologies are best suited for addressing specific learning needs of the students. To note the common problem of teachers is technology related since there is really limited resources to be used. With this, teachers don’t have any choice but to make necessary adjustments but sometimes they are not enough to address the needs of the students.

This result is further supported by the observation tool gathered by the researcher. The key points always focus on commendable teaching strategies (e.g. motivation, discussion and activities) and mastery of the lesson with needs improvement in integration and localization. Least mentioned is the utilization of the ICT to address the needs of the students and to further improve learning process.

This is aligned to what the study of Bevins and price (2019) showed that teachers demonstrated concern about what they view as a lack of quality facilities and equipment. This can be supported also by Baylor and Ritchie (2019) who said that teacher technology competency was predicted by teacher openness to change. These studies proved that aside from support factor of the government in facilities other hindrance also include personal factor which is the acceptance of teachers to change.

Students’ assessment on the Technological Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) and Content Knowledge (CK) of their teachers in terms of Best Practices

Table 16.2. *The Students’ assessment on the Technological Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) and Content Knowledge (CK) of their teachers in terms of Best Practices*

	Best Practices	Teacher			Students			Overall		Rank
		f	%	Rank	F	%	Rank	f	%	
1.	Delineating what content knowledge need to know, how that content knowledge can be taught which includes knowledge about instructional techniques and methods and how technology can facilitate the delivery of instruction	48	52.2	9	397	87.3	2	445	81.4	3
2.	Developing appropriate instructional strategies and skills that are suitable for the 21st century learner.	72	78.3	1	377	82.9	3	449	82.1	2
3.	Identifying important issues in any discussion.	61	66.3	3	357	78.5	4.5	418	76.4	4
4.	Tailoring lesson plans that respond to each students’ needs using technology.	52	56.5	5.5	320	70.3	7	372	68.0	7.5
5.	Modeling a tech-enhanced activity	45	48.9	10	325	71.4	6	370	67.6	9
6.	Developing content specific activities	49	53.3	8	357	78.5	4.5	406	74.2	5
7.	Designing an authentic learning tasks	52	56.5	5.5	320	70.3	7	372	68.0	7.5
8.	Integrating pedagogy in modeled lesson	51	55.4	7	279	61.3	10	330	60.3	10
9.	Bridging the gap between theory and practical work	56	60.9	4	320	70.3	7	376	68.7	6
10.	Creating an engaging learning environment	63	68.5	2	398	87.5	1	461	84.3	1

As presented on the table, the teacher-respondents considered item no. 2 “Developing appropriate instructional strategies and skills that are suitable for the 21st century learner.” as their rank 1 with 78.3%. Rank 10 is item no. 5 “Modeling a tech-enhanced activity” with 48.9%.

When it comes to students, rank 1 is item no. 10 “Creating an engaging learning environment.” with 87.5%. The last in rank is item no. 8 “Integrating pedagogy in modeled lesson.” with 61.3%.

With regards to overall result, rank 1 is item no. 10 “Creating an engaging learning environment.” with 84.3% while the last in rank is item no. 8 “Integrate pedagogy in modeled lesson.

It is implied from the result that the teachers considered developing appropriate instructional strategies and skills that are suitable for the 21st century learner. When it comes to students, creating an engaging learning environment is the best. This may mean that teachers ensure that students will be able to have a conducive learning environment that will engage students to healthy learning situation. This includes problem solving and cooperative activities and exposing students to real life situation.

This was further supported by the observation tool that was gathered by the researcher. The result stated that teachers are able to manage classroom structure to engage learners individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments. Teachers are able to provide activities that will cater individual and group learning suitable

to all types of learners. In addition, they are able to combine traditional and modern teaching to provide commendable instructional strategies. Furthermore, they reflect on what to teach, how to teach and what to use to identify every detailed and issues of the lesson so they will be prepared and be able to execute the lesson successfully.

Based on the study of Wagner and Gordon (2020) almost every K–12 school has at least some outdoor space that faculty could use (or already do) to breathe life into concepts learned in the classroom. A more recent study has linked outdoor play to stronger social skills and increased creative development. This proves that teachers have variety of ways and techniques to maximize their strategies to improve their performance and delivery of lesson.

Conclusions

On the basis of the summary of findings, the following conclusions were drawn: Mostly female are engaged into teaching. They are qualified to teach in Junior School since they pursue graduate studies to master their chosen field.

With respect to Technological Knowledge, for teachers they are excellent in applying the principles in instructional material preparations and in designing ICT-based instructional materials with digital resources. However, they are weak in exposing students to E- instructional resources such as E-Books, hyperlinks, and computer-assisted activities. While for students, their teachers are excellent in preparing the instructional materials for different types of learners and applying the principles in instructional material preparations but weak in using improvised and indigenized materials for instruction. This may mean that master teachers are competent in preparing instructional materials using the technology that are suitable to different types of learners. They are able to follow the principles in the preparations that is they can improvise or use ICT-based instructional materials. However, students don't consider the design excellent. With respect to Pedagogical Knowledge, teachers believe that they are excellent in Providing questions based on the level of the students but need to improve in establishing competencies between the lessons and the students' actual environment while for the student, their teachers are very satisfactory in providing feedback mechanism to students to evaluate their performance and serves as basis for improvement and in establishing competencies between the lessons and the students' actual environment. This means that teachers are very competent in almost all aspects of pedagogical approach specially in using (Higher Order Thinking) HOT questions with minimal improvement in relating learning to real life situation but there is a need to address the concerns of the students specifically how they provide feedback mechanism to students to evaluate their performance and serves as basis for improvement. With the contradicting assessment of teachers and students, specifically in providing feedback mechanism to students to evaluate their performance and serves as basis for improvement and establishing competencies between the lessons and the students' actual environment, there is a need to address these needs for improvement. With that it will serve as a basis for the output of the study which is capacity building. With respect to content knowledge intents should be given more emphasis as to how individual learners may master the lesson well. Teachers perceived that they are excellent in designing lessons with congruent objectives, teaching methods, learning activities and materials but can improve more in exposing students to scholarly researches to discover the concepts independently. Meanwhile, the students perceived that their teachers are excellent in updating the knowledge on the subject matter but need to improve in utilizing content-based approaches for individual learners. Furthermore, teachers and students believe that Master teachers are very competent in applying the TPACK framework with respect to Content Knowledge. They are excellent in almost all aspects specifically in designing, planning and delivering the lessons with minimal improvement on teaching approaches for individual learners. This may mean that teachers need to further improve or make necessary adjustment in addressing the individual needs of the students especially in exposing students to scholarly researches to discover the concepts independently and in utilizing content-based approaches for individual learner.

Students are motivated to perform well in their class since the result of their grade manifests that they perform well. The grades of the students clearly revealed that students have commendable academic performance. This also proves that the performance of teachers reflects on the performance of students. As the result of assessment, teachers are excellent if not at least very satisfactory in TPACK framework which was justified but the result of students' performance. Furthermore, this can be proven too as the pandemic occurred and all teachers are shifting to other mode of learnings and all were trying to adapt, this too reflects to low performance of students.

Age of teachers does not matter in the utilization of the TPACK framework. Their adaptation on technological knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge (TPACK) framework do not merely rely on their age. Teachers, as they aged perform better and developed more skills to comply with needs of the framework. Moreover, what ever the age of the teachers, they are all equally trained by the schools through LAC sessions and mentoring. Sex of teachers does not matter in applying the TPACK framework in their teaching. Sex does not affect the application of the TPACK framework since both sexes are required to acquire skills in all competencies to be able to comply with the needs of performing teachers. And as observed, whatever the sex of the teachers, they both utilized all aspects of TPACK framework. Grade level cannot be considered as one of the factors that may affect the utilization of the TPACK framework. Whatever the grade level of the teachers, their skills in applying the framework are not affected since teachers use appropriate aspect of the framework depending upon on the level of their students. Educational background of teachers does not contribute in the application of the TPACK framework. Their skills in applying the TPACK framework are not affected by their educational achievements since the competencies associated with the TPACK framework may also be acquired through various seminars and training which are offered by DepEd or through LAC sessions. Seasoned teachers have advantage in applying the TPACK framework. Teachers who have more experience can easily adjust and apply the framework since they already acquire so much

knowledge and experience in applying teaching strategies as they acquired more years in teaching. They have edge in accumulating more knowledge and experience as they have longer years in the profession.

Performance of students does not vary in their age and grade level but it may differ depending on sex since focus, opinion and motivation vary depending on their sexual identity. Grade level is mandatory which means the students' skills are inclined to it and hone depending on each level. Age is just a number that could not be solely use as a basis of understanding a specific matter. This may mean too that sex of students is really a considerable factor since personality of male and female varies specially on focus and dedication to studies.

Students proved the personal assessment of teachers that they are really performing excellently in utilizing the TPACK framework especially in Technological and Content Knowledge. However, teachers need time to reflect and evaluate themselves in their pedagogical knowledge since students slightly don't agree with it. Furthermore, teachers need to consider that pedagogical knowledge is contributory to students' academic performance. Tasks given should be evaluated and improved. Teachers must be aware that their performance reflect on students' performance, with this, if teachers improved students will also improve.

Teachers' performance is significantly related to students' performance. If the teachers have higher competencies they reflect on students' academic performance, with this, the students acquire the same competencies and able to perform well. If the teachers have very good performance, the students are very good as well. Moreover, technological knowledge has very limited contribution on students' performance but pedagogical knowledge and content knowledge of teachers motivate them to strive. This may mean too that whether the teachers use cartolina or manila paper or poster as long as they apply effective strategy and they are knowledgeable with the topic they will be commendable. Teachers must realized that being the best in all aspects of the framework are non-negotiable since they are the key instruments in achieving commendable learning process.

As per students assessment of the Technological Knowledge (TK), Pedagogical Knowledge (PK) and Content Knowledge (CK) of their teachers in terms of problems encountered and best practices the teachers considered limited resources as the most encountered problem in applying Technological, Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework while for students is the need to identify which specific technologies are best suited for addressing specific learning needs of the students. To note the common problem of teachers is technology related since there is really limited resources to be used. With this, teachers don't have any choice but to make necessary adjustments but sometimes they are not enough to address the needs of the students. This result is further supported by the observation tool gathered by the researcher. The key points always focus on commendable teaching strategies (e.g. motivation, discussion and activities) and mastery of the lesson with needs improvement in integration and localization. Least mentioned is the utilization of the ICT to address the needs of the students and to further improve learning process. The teachers considered developing appropriate instructional strategies and skills that are suitable for the 21st century learner. When it comes to students, creating an engaging learning environment is the best. This may mean that teachers ensure that students will be able to have a conducive learning environment that will engage students to healthy learning situation. This includes problem solving and cooperative activities and exposing students to real life situation. This was further supported by the observation tool that was gathered by the researcher. The result stated that teachers are able to manage classroom structure to engage learners individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments. Teachers are able to provide activities that will cater individual and group learning suitable to all types of learners. In addition, they are able to combine traditional and modern teaching to provide commendable instructional strategies. Furthermore, they reflect on what to teach, how to teach and what to use to identify every detailed and issues of the lesson so they will be prepared and be able to execute the lesson successfully.

In line with the conclusions, the following are recommended: The DepEd Division Office should initiate series of trainings that will be focused on tasked based approach that will lead to content realization. The DepEd Division Office should provide feedback mechanism that will evaluate the performance of students. Schools should include in their School Learning Action Cell (SLAC) Session the evaluation of instructional material (IM) to ensure its variation. They have to ensure that IM is not merely a presentation but an audio visual too and entertaining. Additional guidelines through a DepEd Order may be issued by DepEd for additional training for teachers that focus on technological, pedagogical and content knowledge of teachers. Safeguard firm compliance to DO 42, s. 2017 or the National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers to support teachers, and taking awareness on clear evidence that good teachers are vital to improve students' achievement. For the future researchers, further study is recommended, considering larger setting and additional variables.

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